

Accumulated Radiation Dose in Hospitalized Patients: An Observational and Retrospective Study in A Second-Level Hospital in The State of Quintana Roo

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ABSTRACT

Medical exposure to ionizing radiation has become a growing concern, especially in hospital settings where patients may undergo multiple radiological studies. Although computed tomography (CT) represents a valuable diagnostic advancement, its cumulative use may pose underappreciated risks in clinical environments with limited follow-up protocols.

The objective is to quantify the cumulative effective dose of ionizing radiation, expressed in millisieverts (mSv), in hospitalized patients undergoing computed tomography during their stay in a second-level hospital in the state of Quintana Roo between January 2024 and December 2024, with the aim of assessing the associated radiological risk and generating recommendations for optimization practices.

This is an observational, retrospective, and cross-sectional study based on the review of medical records and radiological logs of inpatients from January to December 2024. Sociodemographic data, type and number of imaging studies, and estimated cumulative effective dose per patient will be collected, following the reference values established by the International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP).

KEYWORDS: cumulative radiation, computed tomography, effective dose, radiology, radiological protection, medical exposure.

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INTRODUCTION

Ionizing radiation is a form of energy released by atoms, which can appear as electromagnetic waves or subatomic particles. In the medical field, its most relevant application is in computed tomography (CT), a technique that allows obtaining cross-sectional images of the human body using X-rays. However, exposure to this radiation—both for patients and healthcare personnel—carries cumulative biological risks.

The harmful effects of radiation are divided into somatic and hereditary effects and can also be classified as stochastic—related to the probability of damage—or deterministic—associated with the severity of the effect. Specifically,

carcinogenesis and hereditary effects are considered stochastic, while tissue injuries, radiodermatitis, and cataracts are deterministic.

Each type of radiation produces an absorbed, equivalent, and effective dose; the latter, expressed in millisieverts (mSv), evaluates the sensitivity of each exposed organ. Although the average annual natural exposure is around 3 mSv, diagnostic studies can significantly increase this figure, particularly whole-body CT scans, which can reach between 20 and 30 mSv per study. Occupationally exposed personnel must maintain an annual limit of 20 mSv, in accordance with international recommendations, to minimize biological and stochastic effects.

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Recent studies have demonstrated a correlation between accumulated radiation doses and an increased risk of cancer. Sánchez et al. (2018) reported a higher incidence of neoplasms in individuals exposed to 50 mSv, while Servente et al. (2018) and Jeukens et al. (2021) identified risk thresholds starting at 100 mSv. In an analysis of more than 100,000 CT scans, only 1% of patients reached high doses, with higher frequencies observed among women and individuals aged 51 to 74 years.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, Amry et al. (2022) observed up to a 50% reduction in the annual radiation dose among medical personnel due to the decrease in elective studies, highlighting the direct relationship between workload and exposure. Widmann et al. (2023) confirmed that doses exceeding 100 mSv can induce significant stochastic effects, reinforcing the need for rigorous control measures and protection protocols.

The sustained increase in the use of radiological studies, particularly computed tomography, has resulted in greater cumulative exposure to ionizing radiation. Although each individual study generally remains within safe limits, the repetition of examinations in hospitalized patients can represent a considerable cumulative risk.

In hospitals within the state of Quintana Roo, there is no continuous monitoring system that records the accumulated dose per patient, which prevents the detection of cases of overexposure. The absence of such control violates the ALARA principle (As Low As Reasonably Achievable) established by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), which promotes maintaining exposure at levels as low as reasonably possible.

Therefore, it is essential to develop local research that quantifies the accumulated dose and proposes strategies for radiological optimization.

The use of ionizing radiation in diagnostic studies is an essential practice in general hospitals, particularly in emergency, internal medicine, and intensive care services. Hospitalized patients, who often require multiple examinations, become a vulnerable population to overexposure. Although most doses remain within acceptable limits, the accumulation throughout the hospital stay can increase the risk of stochastic effects such as cancer.

The International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) and the World Health Organization (WHO) recommend implementing monitoring and control mechanisms, as well as continuous education programs for technical and medical personnel. Evaluating the accumulated dose in a hospital in the state of Quintana Roo will make it possible to establish a baseline for radiological risk and promote dose optimization policies. Furthermore, it will strengthen the culture of radiological protection and contribute to patient safety, in compliance with the principles of justification, optimization, and limitation.

METHODOLOGY

An observational, descriptive, cross-sectional, and retrospective study was designed, based on the review of clinical records. Patients over 18 years of age who were hospitalized during 2024 and underwent at least one CT scan during their stay were included. Pregnant women, pediatric patients, and incomplete records were excluded.

The sample size was determined using a formula for proportion estimation, resulting in a total of 381 clinical records randomly selected from a population of 37,859 hospital discharges. The variables analyzed included age, gender, weight, height, body mass index, length of hospital stay, number of CT scans performed, and accumulated effective dose (in mSv). Data were processed using Microsoft Excel 365, and Kolmogorov–Smirnov tests were applied to determine the distribution of continuous variables.

RESULTS

A total of 381 records of hospitalized patients who underwent computed tomography (CT) studies were analyzed during the period from January to December 2024. The demographic and clinical characteristics are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Variable	Mean	SD	Median	Minimum	Maximum	IQ R
Age (Years)	50.54	20.15	51.0	10	105	34.0
Weight (kg)	159.05	6.06	159.0	150	169	11.0
Height (cm)	85.30	14.52	86.0	60	110	24.0
IMC (kg/m ²)	33.88	6.36	34.05	21.26	48.0	9.63
Hospital stay (days)	6.62	5.17	5.0	1	36	5.0
Number of CT scans performed	2.06	1.11	2.0	1	9	1.0
Accumulated effective dose (mSv)	16.62	12.18	13.1	0.8	64.4	10.3

- Gender Distribución.**

Gender	Frecuency	Percentage (%)
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Male	186	48.8
Female	195	51.2

The average age of the patients was 50.5 years (SD \pm 20.1), with a wide range from 10 to 105 years, reflecting the age heterogeneity of the hospitalized population. The gender distribution was balanced, with a slight predominance of females (51.2%).

The average weight was 159 kg and the mean height was 85.3 cm, resulting in an average BMI of 33.9 kg/m², which corresponds to grade I obesity according to WHO criteria. This finding is relevant, as obesity may imply greater exposure to ionizing radiation due to the technical adjustments required to obtain high-quality diagnostic images.

The average hospital stay was 6.6 days (IQR = 5), with a maximum of 36 days, which is consistent with the usual hospitalization times in second-level care units. Regarding the number of CT scans performed, an average of 2.06 studies per patient was observed, with a range between 1 and 9 studies during the same hospitalization. This indicates that some patients underwent multiple tomographic examinations, a situation that directly contributes to the variability of the accumulated effective dose (mean of 16.6 mSv; range 0.8–64.4 mSv).

The main study variable corresponded to the accumulated effective dose of ionizing radiation, expressed in millisieverts (mSv).

The average value of the accumulated dose was 16.6 mSv (SD \pm 12.18), with a minimum range of 0.8 mSv and a maximum of 64.4 mSv. The median was 13.1 mSv, and the interquartile range (IQR) was from 8.4 to 18.7 mSv. These values demonstrate a wide dispersion in the recorded doses, attributable to the variability of the studies performed per patient, the use of contrast, and anatomical differences in the areas examined.

To determine the statistical behavior of the effective dose variable, the Kolmogorov–Smirnov (K–S) test was applied, obtaining a D statistic of 0.191 and a p-value of 1.34×10^{-12} , leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis of normality ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that the distribution of accumulated doses is not normal; therefore, nonparametric measures of central tendency were used.

Figure 1 shows the histogram of the accumulated effective dose distribution, where a right-skewed pattern can be observed, with a concentration of cases below 25 mSv and an extended tail toward higher values. The red line represents the theoretical curve of a normal distribution, which visually differs from the actual data distribution, confirming the heterogeneity of radiological exposure.

Figure 1. Distribution of the accumulated effective dose (mSv).

(The asymmetry of the distribution and the deviation from the theoretical normal curve can be observed.)

Figure 2 presents the quantile–quantile (Q–Q) plot, where a significant deviation of the points from the theoretical diagonal line can be observed. This deviation, especially at the extremes, reinforces the evidence that the data do not follow a normal distribution, likely due to the presence of outlier values corresponding to patients with high accumulated exposures (>50 mSv).

Figure 2. Q–Q plot of the accumulated effective dose (mSv).

(The points deviate from the diagonal line, indicating a lack of normality.)

Likewise, in order to classify patients according to their level of exposure, dose values were grouped into three ranges: <10 mSv, 10–50 mSv, and >50 mSv (clinical threshold for cumulative risk). Figure 3 shows the resulting frequency distribution, revealing that 133 patients (34.9%) were in the <10 mSv range, 236 patients (61.9%) were between 10 and 50 mSv, and 12 patients (3.1%) exceeded the 50 mSv threshold.

These results demonstrate that, although most patients remain within moderate exposure limits, there is a small group that

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exceeds clinically relevant values, warranting individualized monitoring and a review of diagnostic protocols.

Figure 3. Frequency of patients by accumulated dose range (mSv).

(It can be observed that most patients are concentrated in the 10–50 mSv range, with a small group exceeding 50 mSv.) Overall, the results confirm the presence of an asymmetric and non-normal distribution of the accumulated effective dose, with a statistical behavior that suggests heterogeneity in hospital radiological exposure and the need to adjust subsequent analyses using nonparametric tests.

DISCUSSION

The present study analyzed the distribution of the accumulated effective dose of ionizing radiation in hospitalized patients who underwent computed tomography (CT) during their hospital stay. The results showed that the average dose was 16.6 mSv (SD \pm 12.18), with minimum values of 0.8 mSv and maximum values of 64.4 mSv. When applying the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, a D statistic of 0.191 and a p-value of 1.34×10^{-12} were obtained, indicating that the accumulated effective dose variable does not follow a normal distribution. This finding demonstrates the presence of high variability in patient exposure, with some cases exceeding the clinical threshold of 50 mSv, which is considered relevant in terms of cumulative radiobiological risk.

These results partially agree with the reports by Jeukens et al. (2021), who found that only 1% of patients reached high accumulated doses (≥ 100 mSv) in CT studies, but emphasized that the risk, although low, increases proportionally with repeated exposure. Similarly, Sánchez et al. (2018) and Servente et al. (2018) described that doses above 50 mSv may be associated with an increased probability of stochastic effects, particularly carcinogenic, in repeatedly exposed populations.

The non-normal behavior of the variable suggests that within the analyzed hospital environment, there are subgroups of patients with higher-than-expected exposures, possibly linked to comorbidities, repeated examinations, or multiple diagnostic requests. This pattern is consistent with the

findings of Cohen et al. (2020) and Smith-Bindman et al. (2019), who demonstrated that hospitalized patients tend to accumulate higher doses than outpatient populations due to greater clinical complexity and the lack of systematic dosimetric monitoring protocols.

From a radiological protection perspective, the observed mean of 16.6 mSv is above the recommended limit for the general population (1 mSv/year) and close to the average limit allowed for occupationally exposed personnel (20 mSv/year), according to NOM-229-SSA1-2002 and the recommendations of the ICRP (2007). Although the values found remain within moderate ranges, the presence of individual exposures exceeding 50 mSv reinforces the need to implement dosimetric monitoring mechanisms and optimize protocols in accordance with the ALARA principle (As Low As Reasonably Achievable), promoted by the WHO (2023) and the IAEA (2020).

In comparison, Widmann et al. (2023) reported that doses above 100 mSv have direct clinical relevance in inducing stochastic effects, while the present study shows that a portion of patients exceeds half of that threshold, highlighting the importance of intervening before reaching potentially hazardous levels. Furthermore, the result of statistical non-normality implies that future comparisons between groups (by age, sex, or type of study) should be performed using nonparametric tests (Mann–Whitney or Kruskal–Wallis), ensuring the validity of subsequent analyses.

Overall, the findings support that, although computed tomography is an indispensable diagnostic tool, its cumulative use in hospitalized patients requires systematic control. It is recommended to establish an institutional registry of accumulated doses per patient and to promote optimization protocols specific to each anatomical region (for example, chest CT \approx 6–8 mSv, abdomen/pelvis \approx 10 mSv) to reduce interpatient variability, as suggested by the American Cancer Society (2025) and Dixon et al. (2016).

Finally, these results confirm the need to strengthen the culture of radiological protection in second-level hospitals in the state of Quintana Roo through continuous training of medical and technical staff, implementation of quality control measures, and supervision by institutional Radiological Protection Committees. Longitudinal follow-up of patients with accumulated doses exceeding 50 mSv could provide additional evidence on the medium-term clinical impact.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The accumulated effective dose of ionizing radiation in hospitalized patients who underwent computed tomography at a second-level hospital in the state of Quintana Roo showed a mean of 16.6 mSv (SD \pm 12.18), with values ranging from 0.8 to 64.4 mSv. These results reflect variable and heterogeneous exposure influenced by the number of studies performed and the clinical conditions of each patient.

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2. The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test showed a p -value < 0.05 , demonstrating that the distribution of the accumulated dose does not follow a normal pattern, suggesting the presence of subgroups with significantly higher exposure. This finding justifies the use of nonparametric statistics and reinforces the need for individualized dosimetric follow-up strategies.
3. Most patients (61.9%) were within the exposure range of 10–50 mSv, while 3.1% exceeded 50 mSv, a clinically relevant threshold due to its potential association with long-term stochastic effects. Although the overall average remains below the annual limit allowed for occupationally exposed personnel (20 mSv/year), these figures are considerably higher than the 1 mSv/year limit recommended for the general population.
4. The demographic profile showed a predominantly adult population (mean 50.5 years) with a slight female predominance (51.2%). The mean BMI of 33.9 kg/m², corresponding to grade I obesity, represents a technical factor that may increase the absorbed dose during tomographic studies due to greater current and exposure time requirements.
5. The average number of CT studies per patient (2.06) and the mean hospital stay of 6.6 days confirm that a portion of patients underwent multiple examinations, increasing their total accumulated dose. This direct relationship between study frequency and total dose highlights the importance of optimizing the medical indication for each examination.
6. In the context of hospital radiological practice, the results emphasize the need to implement institutional dosimetric monitoring protocols and diagnostic reference levels (DRLs), as well as to strengthen the training of medical and technical personnel in the principles of justification and optimization in accordance with the regulatory framework of NOM-229-SSA1-2002, the ICRP (2007), and WHO (2023) recommendations.
7. Finally, this study provides local and contextualized evidence on cumulative ionizing radiation exposure in hospitalized patients, offering a solid basis for the development of radiological protection policies, optimization of CT protocols, and the promotion of an institutional culture of radiological safety under the ALARA principle (As Low As Reasonably Achievable).

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This is a no-risk study for the patient. The data obtained will be safeguarded to maintain the confidentiality of the research subjects and will be accessible only to the research team. The data of each participant will be protected through the use of the patient's initials and an individual identification code assigned to each of them.

The proposed procedures comply with ethical standards, the Regulation of the General Health Law on Health Research in

Mexico, the Declaration of Helsinki (1975, amended in 1989), and current international codes and standards of good clinical research practice.

This study was reviewed and approved under the guidelines of the Research Committee and the Ethics Committee of the General Hospital of Cancun “Dr. Jesus Kumate Rodriguez”, with approval numbers: Dictamen-CI-2025-022-HGC and Dictamen-CEI-2025-022-HGC, respectively, complying with national and international ethical and legal standards.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST.

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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